

Global Monsoon Time Scale

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The global Monsoon Time Scale – a Chronological sequence of events arranged in between time and weather with the help of a scale for studying the past's, present and future movements of monsoon of a country and its relationship with rainfall and other weather problem and natural calamities.

Prepare the Global Monsoon Time Scale having 365 horizontal days from March 21st to next year March 20th of a required period comprising of a large time and weather have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale. The main weather events if any of the country have been entering on the scale as per date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale of a country in this manner continuously, we can study the past, present and future movements of monsoon of a country. We can make separate monsoon time scales per each and every individual country.

INDIAN MONSOON TIME SCALE:

For example, I have prepared the monsoon time scale for India by preparing the scale having 365 horizontal days from 1st April to next year March 31st of 128 years from 1888 to 2016 of the required period comprising of large time and weather have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale. The monsoon pulses in the form of low pressure systems over the Indian region have been entering on the scale in stages by 1 for low, 2 for depression, 3 for storm, 4 for severe storm and 5 for severe storm with core of hurricane winds pertaining to the date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale in this manner continuously, we can study the past' present's and futures of the India Monsoon and its relationship with rainfall and other weather problems & natural calamities in India.

ANALYSIS:

The India Monsoon Time Scale reveals many secrets of the Indian monsoon and its relationship with rainfall & other weather problems and natural calamities. For example, some bands, clusters and paths of low pressure systems along with the main paths of the Indian Monsoon (South-east monsoon and north-west monsoon) clearly seen in the map of the Indian monsoon it have been some cut-edged paths passing through its systematic zigzag cycles in ascending and descending orders which causes heavy rains & floods in some years and droughts & famines in another years according to their travel. For example, during 1871-1990's, the main path of the Indian Monsoon was rising over June, July, August and creating heavy rains and floods in most years. During 1900-1920's, it was rising over August, September and resulting good rainfall in more years. During 1965-2004's it was falling over September and causing low rainfall and droughts in many years. At present it is rising upwards over June, July, August, September and will be resulting heavy rains & floods in coming years during 2004-2060. The tracking date of main path & other various paths such as south-east monsoon and north-west monsoon etc., of the Indian Monsoon denotes the onset of the monsoon, monsoon pulses or low pressure systems. And also we can find out many more secrets of the Indian monsoon such as droughts, famines, cyclones, heavy rains, floods, real images of the Indian monsoon, and onset & withdrawals of south east monsoon and north-west monsoon etc. by keen study of the Indian Monsoon Time Scale.

PRINCIPLE:

This is an Astrogeophysical/Astrometeorological phenomenon of effects of astronomical bodies and forces on the earth's geophysical atmosphere. The cause is unknown however the year to year change of movement of axis of the earth inclined at 23½ degrees from vertical to its path around the sun does play a significant role in formation of clusters, bands & paths of the Indian Monsoon and stimulates the Indian weather. The inter-

tropical convergence zone at the equator follows the movement of the sun and shifts north of the equator merges with the heat low pressure zone created by the rising heat of the sub-continent due to direct and converging rays of the summer sun on the India Sub-Continent and develops into the monsoon trough and maintain monsoon circulation.

CONCLUSION:

We can make many more modifications thus bringing many more developments in the Global Monsoon Time Scale. We can also make many more changes and development in the monsoon time scales and make separate monsoon time scales in name of each and every country of the world in accordance with the weather circumstances of the countries.

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

Basic Scale 1/4

filled Scaled 1/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

ANALYSIS OF MONSOON

Basic Scale 1/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

Cut up to bottom along with line here & paste along with line to 2/4

THE ITCZ SET FORTH OVER EQUATOR Trade Winds Converge at the ITCZ of I.e. a low pressure region at the equator The ITCZ Moves north wards over the indian region The ITCZ passing over the Andhra Pradesh

INDIAN WEATHER

-74-

Basic Scale 2/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS
TIMES SCALE

Cut up to bottom along with line here & paste along with line to 3/4

TIMES SCALE

-75-

Basic Scale 3/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

THE ITCZ SET FORTH OVER EQUATOR 4
 Trade Winds Converge at the ITCZ of i.e. a low pressure region at the equator 8
 The ITCZ Moves north wards over the Indian region 12
 The ITCZ passing over the Andhra Pradesh 16

Cut up to bottom along with line here 8 paste along with line to 4/4

Basic Scale 4/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS
TIMES SCALE

Path Of Sun
Weather Cycle Experimental Data

THE ITCZ SET FORTH OVER EQUATOR Trade Winds Converge at the ITCZ of i.e. a low pressure region at the equator The ITCZ Moves north wards over the indian region The ITCZ passing over the Andhra Pradesh

filled Scaled 1/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

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SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

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filled Scaled 4/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

THE ITCZ SET IN OVER EQUATOR Trade Winds Converge at the ITCZ of i.e. a low pressure region at the equator The ITCZ Moves north wards over the Indian region The ITCZ passing over the Andhra Pradesh

INDIAN MONSOON

Analysed Scale 2/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

TIME SCALE

winter Solstic

Analysed Scale 3/4

Analysed Scale 4/4

SOUTH EAST TRADE WINDS

INDIAN MONSOON TIME SCALE

INDIAN MONSOON TIME SCALE

Abridged analysed scale from 1888 year to 2018 year for the months of May 1st to December, 31st

MAP OF THE INDIAN MONSOON

ANALYSIS OF Years (1888-1983)

ANALYSIS OF Months (JUN-SEP)

Table with columns for years (1888-1983) and months (JUN, JUL, AUGUST, SEPTEMBER). The table contains a grid of binary data (0s and 1s) representing monsoon analysis.

Computerised basic scale from 1888 year to 1983 year for the months of 1st June to September, 31st

path of the systematic cycle of the Indian Monsoon.

Computerised analysed scale from 1888 year to 1983 year for the months of 1st June to September, 31st.